

SOME ASPECTS OF STRENGTHENING THE WELFARE STATE AND YOUTH ACTIVITY

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ANNOTATION

This article focuses on issues related to the welfare state and some aspects of youth activity. Consequently, the essence of the content of the concept of the welfare state, the views of scientists involved in this field, and the specifics of the social activity of young people and youth are highlighted. In addition, the tasks of the Action strategy reflect pragmatic changes in the lives of young people, defined on the principles of the Development strategy.

Basic concepts: *welfare state, youth activity, human potential, evolutionism of reforms, social justice, social law, sustainable development.*

INTRODUCTION

The philosophical content of the concept of the welfare state and youth activity. As you know, considering the history of national statehood, you can observe a huge number of forms of statehood. It is appropriate to include bourgeois, socialist, democratic, etc. Since 2017, in the conditions of the new Uzbekistan, it has been established that "The people should serve the people, not government institutions, but rather state structures"[1]. Based on this, article 1 of the updated Constitution was changed to "Uzbekistan is a sovereign, democratic, legal, social and secular state with a republican form of government." In fact, the concept of a "welfare state" is closely related to the idea of "human dignity" [2]. They are based, first of all, on noble goals, such as the glorification of universal values, service to the people. Consequently, the essence of the welfare state covers the issues of creating decent living conditions for every person on the principles of equality and justice. According to our president, "The welfare state is, first of all, equal opportunities for realizing human potential, creating the necessary conditions for a decent life for people, reducing poverty!"[3]. The economic sphere is important when it comes to the social sphere. The economic upswing opens up new prospects and opportunities in people's lives. Today, the developed countries of the world are trying to take a leading position in other areas. It can be said that after Uzbekistan gained independence, development along a new economic path became a top priority. The reason is that the communist system has

reduced interest in innovation in people's lives, caused a state of depression and stagnation in society.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

In preparing this article, a number of scientific studies were studied under the topic "Some aspects of strengthening the welfare state and youth activism". In particular, A.A. Klishas, who is associated with the welfare state. The monograph "The search for a social state", prepared by A.A. Klishas "Socialization of youth: the experience of positive analysis" by S. L. Talanova, "The concept of a social state: his theoretical and practical studies" by I.V. Mikhalev, as well as the works of G. L. Smirnov, such as "The Essence of Freedom" and "Freedom of the individual", served as the methodological basis of this topic. In addition, local participates in this field from the scientist, Doctor of Political Sciences, Professor S.Juraev, in the direction of youth issues D.Buranov, Sh.T.Mamatkulov, J.Mirakhmedov some researches have been implemented. When covering a scientific article, such methods as analysis-synthesis, systematic analysis, content analysis and the like were used.

RESULTS

After gaining independence, a solid foundation was created in Uzbekistan for the transition to a market economy. It is based on our wise people, in particular, our entrepreneurs, large fields favorable for agriculture, our underground and surface resources. Due to its economic potential, our country, which has huge opportunities, occupies a worthy place in the world community. The welfare State is a qualitative characteristic of the state in terms of its constitutional and legal status, which assumes that the economic, social rights and freedoms of man and citizen and the corresponding duties of the State are guaranteed by the Constitution. The welfare State seeks to reduce or eliminate social differences in it, serving the common interests of society. The social character of the State is in many cases enshrined in its Basic Law. In 1949, the Constitution of the TFR was adopted for the first time, and in subsequent years in other European states, sociality found its fundamental expression in the constitutions of the CIS states [5]. The welfare State is obliged to protect people's work and health, establish a minimum guaranteed wage, provide assistance to the family, motherhood, fatherhood and childhood, the disabled and the elderly, guarantee state pensions, benefits and other types of social protection. The material basis of a welfare state is a high level of economic development that can provide a living wage for low-income segments of the population.

Naturally, for a more complete understanding of the nature of the welfare state, it is advisable to study it from the point of view of progress, as well as views and approaches to it. For example, in Ancient Greece, social policy was also carried out by the ancient Roman state in the provinces in order to ensure the trust and loyalty of the conquered population to the country [6]. Social policy was carried out in subsequent historical periods — in Europe and in modern states in the Middle Ages.

At the same time, until the middle of the 19th century, when social support measures were scattered, they were also introduced mainly to ensure the support of the ruling class, and social policy did not have a clear theoretical basis [7]. If you pay attention to the etymology of the welfare state, then, for example, the term "welfare state" used in Russian comes from the German word Sozialstaat. At the same time, the English-language literature uses the term welfare state, which translates as the welfare state [8]. It can be seen that these terms have different semantic content: "social state" indicates the social orientation of state policy, the desire to ensure a high level of social guarantees; "social state" characterizes the qualitative state of already established social relations, indicates that the goals of social policy have been achieved. Thus, the concept of a "social state" seems to more accurately express the meaning of the identified phenomenon.

At the same time, as part of further research, these terms are used synonymously. The Encyclopedia Britannica defines the welfare state as a concept of public administration in which the State or a well-established network of social institutions play an important role in protecting and improving the economic and social well-being of citizens. This concept is based on the principles of equality of opportunity, equal distribution of wealth and social responsibility for those who cannot provide themselves with the minimum means to ensure a good life [9]. The Cambridge Dictionary says that a welfare state is a system in which the government takes care of people with disabilities, the elderly, or those who cannot find work, and pays for them. Duden's German dictionary shows that a welfare state is a democratic state that seeks to ensure the economic security of its citizens and balance social differences within society [10]. The International Comprehensive Dictionary of Social and Behavioral Sciences, on the other hand, defines a welfare State as a State that seeks to ensure its basic economic security by protecting its citizens from market risks associated with old age, unemployment, accidents and diseases. In Russian constitutional and legal science, 10 different approaches to the definition of a welfare state have been proposed.

Considering to O.E.Kutafin argues that "The main task of the welfare state is to achieve social development based on the principles of social justice, universal solidarity and mutual responsibility enshrined in law. The welfare state is designed to help the weak, influence the distribution of economic benefits based on the principle of justice, and ensure a decent life for all [11]." Russian scientist V.E. Chirkin, "A social state is an active, regulating state that intervenes primarily in socio-economic relations and relations in the field of culture, spiritual life, ultimately for general (public) purposes, although this does not always correspond to them (and its activities). Such a position cannot equally take into account the interests of all sectors of society and individuals [12]." According to M.V.Baglay: "A social state is a state that is obliged to take care of social justice, the welfare of its citizens and their social

security." The Danish sociologist J. Esping-Anderson identified the following models of welfare states in a study of U.S. social policy in 18 states conducted in 1980: - A liberal model according to which many benefits, such as health insurance and pensions, depend on employment. To determine the right to use public services, a test is used for the need to receive social benefits and benefits vouchers, and those who deem it appropriate are provided with a relatively small number of cash benefits and vouchers.; - for example, the conservative/corporate model implemented in Germany is based on the provision of services by the state, and not on market or private services [13]. In the model under consideration, normative ideals of the family are often manifested, which are considered basic, characterized by a male breadwinner and a woman who takes care of the family.

In general, the socio-democratic model typical of the Scandinavian countries and, in particular, Sweden, is based on the idea that the state acts as a guarantor. Obviously, this classification is simplified in nature — any classification involves taking into account only certain, most important factors that make it possible to determine the ideal models of something. At the same time, it is necessary to take into account the cultural, linguistic, behavioral and other characteristics of each individual country, which, of course, will not always be able to do this sufficiently. In this regard, D. Mitchell identified five key criteria for comparing welfare state models in a comparative legal study of welfare states, including a comparison of policies, resources allocated to ensure welfare, rules, benefits and services provided to the population, and the results of social policy implementation [14].

This is the basis of the second important concept related to the topic, which is considered to be related to "youth activism". In our country, on the basis of the rich intellectual and cultural heritage of the people and universal values, comprehensive reforms are being carried out aimed at increasing the activity of young people, educating their spiritual and moral qualities. After all, "The well-being of our planet the next day depends on how much our children grow up as human beings. Our main task is to create the necessary conditions for young people to show their potential [15]." When it comes to such a responsible topic, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan expresses the following thoughts: "We will persistently continue the state policy towards youth, without any deviations. We will not only continue, but also raise this policy as our main priority to the high level that modernity requires. Possessing independent thinking, high intellectual and spiritual potential, our young people mobilize all the forces and capabilities of our state and society so that they can grow up, be happy, and become people who are not inferior to their peers on a global scale in any field [16]." In the implementation of these tasks, the issues of increasing the socio-political activity of young people, the formation of a new worldview for them are of paramount scientific importance. The concept of "activity" is also used primarily as a synonym for the concept of "activity". Human activity acquires a

special meaning and essence as the ability to change the environment in accordance with their needs, views, goals. The relevant literature speaks about the differentiation of personality activity according to a number of characteristics [17]. Summarizing the approaches to this, the following forms of activity can be distinguished:

activity as a form of activity, indicating the essential uniqueness of the concepts of "activity" and "activity approach";

human activity as an activity in which his own inner attitude is formed, his individual experience is reflected;

activity as an activity aimed at changing the environment; activity having personal significance activity as a product of human activity in the form of manifestation of his own personality, as well as familiarization with interaction with his environment.

Based on this, the presence of an indicator indicates that its areas of activity are diverse. The fields of activity are closely related to the activities of people, individuals or strata of a particular social group, and have not been isolated. Social activity is realized in connection with social strata, in particular with the consciousness, worldview, behavior, life goals and aspirations of young people, with their national ideological image. Then the term youth activism, active youth, social youth activism, politically active youth is used. The activities of persons aged 15 to 24 in a public organization aimed at social change are called youth activism. The activity of young people leads to a change in political participation and activism in society. A significant change in youth activity is understood as an increase in "alternative activity", an increase in the effectiveness of the life experience of young activists and attention to communication. Many studies have shown that the effective use of modern technologies and digital media has changed the activity of young people around the world in society, and young people are more active in the media than representatives of the older generation.

The implementation of youth policy in a social state is carried out on a socio-legal basis. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, young people are taken care of as one of the privileged strata of society, and from the first days of our independence, attention has been paid to the consistent implementation of the state youth policy. The issue of comprehensive protection of their interests was reflected in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the National Training Program, the laws "On Education", "On State youth policy", "On guarantees of the rights of the child", "On the prevention of uncontrolled and delinquency among minors", "On the protection of children from information harmful to their health". Only as part of the implementation of the action strategy in 2017, more than 20 laws and more than 700 legislative acts were adopted [18]. Building a just rule of law, forming a free civil society and achieving a comfortable standard of living are high goals that our people strive for. The role of youth in our society in achieving these goals is special.

Therefore, today this issue has become one of the priorities of state policy. The essence, the main directions of this policy, socio-economic and political-legal guarantees provided to youth, clearly defined the social, economic, legal and organizational measures that are the main directions of this sphere in the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On State Youth Policy" dated September 14, 2016"[19]. The law "On the foundations of State Youth Policy in Uzbekistan" [20] defines social protection as a set of guarantees provided to them by the state in order to ensure their physical, mental, moral development and their place in public life in the interests and future of the youth of Uzbekistan. Therefore, Head of State Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted in the UN Youth Strategy that "the youth system embodies the most valuable and extremely important resources that are worth investing every amount in it, since these investments will pay off several times more." I completely agree with this very important opinion. Since the beginning of this year, the situation with the COVID-19 pandemic has become a central issue on the global agenda. The spread of the new coronavirus has led to serious economic and social consequences around the world. The population, primarily young people, has faced many problems that require States and the international community to take large-scale measures in response to these threats. In such circumstances, it is very important to listen to the voice of youth. It is necessary to provide young people with opportunities so that they can directly participate in the development and implementation of national, regional and global strategies and programs aimed at meeting their urgent needs, protecting their rights and legitimate interests [21]."

DISCUSSION

According to experts, the social composition of the population of any country, especially the youth stratum, requires constant orientation and support due to relatively rapid change, dynamic growth and regular formation.

One of the most urgent tasks is for each state to be able to educate the younger generation, who continue their perspective for the future, in the spirit of democratic, universal and national values, and adequately support them in a positive way. The upbringing of the younger generation, which manifests itself as a creator of any society, is always of great importance. It should be noted that more than 60% of the population of Uzbekistan are young people under the age of 30[22]. A person's desire to establish a dialogue with society, a wide audience, and the people arises, first of all, from his desire to show himself, his self in the social space. In this sense, President of the republic of Uzbekistan, called 2021 in our country "the year of youth support and public health promotion" also has a symbolic meaning. In fact, "it is necessary that we educate young people in adulthood as independent and logically thinking people with noble qualities based on modern knowledge and experience, national and universal values [23]."Social life and human interaction are two-sided, dialectical in

nature. The more the social environment affects a person, the more opportunities a person has to influence and change the social environment. Therefore, both sides have their own filter, that is, they receive information that suits them. From this point of view, young people will need a sufficient environment to form healthy beliefs and a high worldview. A lot of work is being done in Uzbekistan in this direction.

First of all, it is necessary to evaluate the social views of young people, their behavior, their interests, their worldview and other aspects, depending on the specifics of a particular period and conditions.

Secondly, the analysis and study of the specific lifestyle of young people. At the same time, the social status of youth, lifestyle and its development are studied theoretically and empirically.

Thirdly, the study and comprehensive analysis of the spiritual behavior of young people. Dynamic study of the constant connection between generations as a result of existing socio-economic conditions, changes in the environment. In fact, young people are the most numerous and mobile part of society. Their constant study is one of the urgent problems of our time.

A modern algorithm for increasing the activity of young people in the development of the welfare state. Although the Action strategy for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021 identifies important tasks related to increasing the activity of young people in reforms to build a democratic state and develop civil society, its implementation in regions and districts is not fully ensured. Most of the young people who have completed their studies are not what they want, they get a job there wherever they have an acquaintance. Personnel potential is not properly assessed, any organization or association that is not knowledgeable in its profession is doomed to crisis. The government system is full of young people who have received education far from management theory, who have graduated from construction, engineering, agricultural, and automotive fields. Some young people working in the system lack communication culture skills. We believe that young people who receive education in the social areas of universities should work in the management system.

Secondly, in Uzbekistan, young people make up more than 60% of the population, while the average age of the country's population is 25 years old. Therefore, it is necessary to pay serious attention to supporting young people by creating additional jobs, as well as opportunities for improving well-being. The success of reforms is inextricably linked with the fact that our country occupies a worthy place among the developed, modern countries of the world, first of all, with the development of the field of Science and education, in this regard, with our ability to be competitive on a global scale [24]. Unfortunately, there is still a massive outflow of young people to neighboring countries in search of work. The activities of

employment services are at a disadvantage, and plans for job creation remain on paper.

As long as the theory does not become a practice, there will be no growth in social processes. To do this, it is necessary to put an end to paperwork, draw conclusions based on the Real situation and objectively assess the situation and switch to practical activities. Life does not stop; the wheel of history cannot be turned back. Social consciousness is of serious importance in the development of society. Because the system is changed by man, the reform is carried out by man. As long as any change is not related to a person, his interests, the sense of responsibility disappears.

Thirdly, Uzbekistan today has 159 institutions of higher education, including 72 in the city of Tashkent, 87 in the regions, but this does not cover all the youth strata of the country. Young people who have lost their passion for reading, for the future, that is, having failed to score enough points, cling to the fact that young men-girls who have fallen from reading stick to the support do not seek help, expressing confidence in the Youth Union organization. Either goes to work abroad, or is depressed and disappointed in life. They would have seen their future in "state youth policy", correctly observing the opportunities given to them and advancing towards their goal, would have had time for a year to both work and learn trades and study.

Fourth, until now, crime among young people has not decreased, instead of a spirit of confidence in the future among young people there are vices such as loquacity, neglect, indulgence, laziness, interest in nothing, insecurity, disobedience, disdain, wanting to get rich quickly, wasting time.

Fifth, issues such as the promotion of a healthy lifestyle among young people, the Prevention of delinquency and crimes among minors, the effective use of media and modern information and communication technologies in the upbringing of a harmonious generation, the support of youth aspirations, their spiritual and physical maturation, the promotion of various foreign ideas and the preservation of low-level

The main goal of the incoming threats under the guise of "Mass culture" is aimed at:

- 1) to spread the ideas of moral perversion and violence, individualism and egocentrism and, therefore, to gain wealth at the expense of;
- 2) how many millennia of traditions and values of other peoples, free access to the spiritual foundations of way of living standard;
- 3) threatening threats aimed at harming them [25].

We are deeply mistaken to say that the threat of " mass culture " penetrates only from the outside. It is natural that any person who is healthy, watching some newspapers, books, some clips and movies being filmed, songs and dances being broadcast, will come to this conclusion [26].

In addition, the export of democracy, the color revolutions and the information attack are now becoming the main means by some Western countries in expanding their national interests. Forces with a mercenary purpose try to implement their ideas through the means of various non-governmental organizations, projects, foundations. In the implementation of such policies, they use the most convenient and fastest, most effective means and methods of information. Information is becoming the main and terrible weapon tool in the hands of some Western countries and international terrorist organizations. The globalization process is directly related to information. From this point of view, today the information factor is becoming in the interest of certain forces, both politically and economically. In a rapidly changing world, responsibility for nations to maintain their values and deliver them to future generations has become an urgent issue [27].

Sixth, no one is interested in the future of girls in which parents are becoming victims of their dreams, reaching adulthood. Parents who marry girls who do not even graduate from college do not worry about the future of the heart of the generation, whether their children have neither a trade nor a profession, cannot stand the blows of marriage and are divorcing one or two children. In the case of young mothers who experience discrimination, corporal punishment, spiritual humiliation, slave-like treatment in the family, the part shows young people that the tasks set in the state program are not provided for their performance in places.

Seventh, today the era itself dictates the need for young people to be active, creative and inquisitive in every aspect, to lay a solid foundation for tomorrow's future from today. The education of representatives of the noble generation in the spirit of loyalty to the motherland, respect for national traditions and values, the implementation of priorities such as ensuring employment, protecting rights and interests, the education, level of intelligibility, intellectual potential, decency, ingenuity, mobility and courage of young people, readiness for change determine the overall level of development of society.

As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoev noted, in the activities of a teacher, a public service teacher, a doctor, a worker, a craftsman, a devotee of each nation, regardless of who they are, a critical analysis, strict discipline and personal responsibility should become a daily rule.

In our opinion, in a rapidly developing society of Science and Technology, Information Technology, the reason why the majority of the youth are surrounded by various problems is due to their worldview, consciousness and thinking. It is imperative and necessary to study the problems and initiatives of youth in each region of our country. Notably, it is not right to say that all young people are socially active. Youth education is the work of both the state and society, which is a priority from family to all organizations of civil society. “An important issue that always makes us think about is the etiquette of young people, their behavior, their worldview. Today

the times are changing rapidly. All these changes are felt by mostly – young people. Let the young people be in harmony with the demands of their time. But don't forget his own too. Let the call “who we are“, “the offspring of what great breeds” give always impact in their hearts and encourage them to remain trustful in themselves. What do we achieve this at the expense of? At the expense of upbringing, upbringing and upbringing alone [28]”.

At the heart of youth Aug state policy is the fundamental improvement and modernization of the processes of education and education of young people, the upbringing of a harmonious generation, the emergence of strong social protection issues, which have its own aspects that the state occupies a leading place in the transformation of young people into a social layer that ensures the future of society. In particular, "It is noteworthy that in today's complex situation, representatives of the younger generation respond appropriately to modern threats, including their promising initiatives and social projects against the pandemic. Throughout the world, volunteer youth are actively involved in supporting the segments of the population in need of assistance, promoting new economic and humanitarian programs [29]”.

A year of 2024- was announced a "Year of Youth and business support ", and the following vases were outlined. We will further strengthen the involvement of foreign investments in our economy, the creation of wide opportunities for entrepreneurship and private property. Special attention is paid to the development of such areas as science, innovation, IT, “Green” and digital technologies.

CONCLUSION

Currently, the importance of youth activism is determined by the fact that the formation of sufficient grounds for their finding a place in social life shows that at the stages of implementing youth policies, they bring up extremely urgent strategic tasks to scientifically study their moods, dreams, hopes, life goals, aspirations and interests in how to live, draw correct conclusions from them,

In our opinion, in order for today's youth to be socially active, independent-minded, thoroughly mastered modern knowledge and profession, able to compete in the international arena, it is necessary to carry out the following aim according:

first, to conduct constant communication with young people, to ensure their employment, to promote their place in life, to allow them to become worthy members of society, to improve working and living conditions;

secondly, providing new jobs for young people, paving the way for their entrepreneurial activities, providing loans for women to practice crafts, retraining and professional development of young people, supporting farming;

We think that the perspective of the country, its place and position in the world community largely depend on the care provided to the younger generation, the conditions created, the physical and spiritual perfection of youth as a person. The

social protection of young people, the improvement of legal foundations aimed at ensuring their needs, the development of related mechanisms to bring their potential to the surface, the formation of leadership skills, especially in the growing young generation, serves as an important factor in ensuring the rights and interests of a harmonious generation. The need to ensure that the above large-scale reforms are sustainable necessitated the reflection of the principle of “social state” in the Constitution. For this reason, most proposals and considerations in the general discussion were precisely oriented towards the social sphere. At the same time, we would not be mistaken to say that the strengthening of our country's status as a social state in our basic law will be both a form and a sense of the essence of the new Uzbekistan.

Today, the need to mature the education of young people, the main layer of the population, unite them on the basis of the ideas of a single Homeland, unity and harmony, encourage new grandiose goals and bold actions, protect against evil ideas of groups, political forces and centers pursuing any ulterior motives is among the pressing issues. The President of the republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoev expressed such thoughts in this regard at the expanded meeting of the Republican Council of spirituality and enlightenment, which took place on December 22, 2023:

- "My dear ones, let us be aware of the unclean ones whose upbringing has gone astray!

- Let's protect our children from their destructive influence!

- We never have the right to put our future in the hands of evil forces.

- If we all act firmly together; we will definitely be able to strengthen a healthy socio-spiritual environment in our society.

- The rule of law in the new Uzbekistan, punishment for crime must be inevitable. And of course it will be” [31].

In general, state policy on youth is a consistent process as an important political direction, which embodies the main features of reality associated with the position and life of young people. In this regard, the state youth policy as a political direction has overtaken all the processes of social changes, fundamental reforms, transformation of youth that took place in the history of the years of independence of Uzbekistan and were purposefully implemented by the state. That is, state youth policy forms a set of efforts and goals carried out to social organization of youth life on democratic principles, building relations between youth and the state on a positive basis, ensuring compliance of youth interests and values with the interests of the state.

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